

ISic3037

Building inscription of bishop Tobias

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

building

Material

stone

Object

unknown

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2019-07-09 - Jonathan Prag revised the file on the basis of work for 2017 edition

Place of origin (ancient)

Halaesa

Place of origin (modern)

near Castel di Tusa

Provenance

Recorded in the Church of S. Maria dei Palazzi by Antonio Agustín c.1559 (codex Matritensis 5781 f.22), but not seen thereafter.

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Lost

Physical Description

No description of the stone is recorded

Dimensions

Height unknown cm

Width unknown cm

Depth unknown cm

Layout

The text is presented over two lines in the transcription

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

In the transcription omega and sigma are lunate, with the sigma made up of three right straight strokes at right-angles; the first two letters are placed one above the other.

Letter heights:

Line 1=2: unknown mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: unknown mm

Text

1. Τωβίας · ἐπίσ(κοπος)

2. ἔκτισεν

Apparatus

Text after Prestianni

T is directly above ω in the transcription

Translation (en)

Bishop Tobias founded (this)

Commentary

The text is one of six that Antonio Agustín recorded as having seen in the church of S. Maria dei Palazzi on the site of Halaesa. Unlike the other five, it was not subsequently recorded by later visitors to the site (cf. e.g. Gualtherus 1624) and has not been seen or recorded since until the edition of Prestianni Giallombardo (1987). There is good reason to believe that Agustín recorded the letter forms accurately, and if so these provide some grounds for a date: the letter forms are comparable to those in the funerary inscription of Eirena (late fourth or fifth century AD) and Prestianni Giallombardo notes Syracusan parallels from the first third of the fifth century AD (1987: 303 n.24). However a substantially later date is also possible, and Prestianni Giallombardo notes firstly that the name Tobias is rare in Sicily, and likely to indicate an immigrant from the eastern Mediterranean, and secondly that there is limited evidence for a bishopric at Halaesa from the seventh century onwards. On this basis she plausibly suggests that Tobias was bishop at Halaesa in the course of the seventh century AD, and the inscription therefore records his construction of a building of some description on the site.

Digital identifiers:

TM 645391

PHI 332166

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Matritensis

Ⲑ ΒΙΑΣ·ΕΠΙΣ
ΕΚΤΙΣΕΝ

Vaticanus Latinus

Ⲑ ΒΙΑΣ·ΕΠΙΣ . . .
ΕΚΤΙΣΕΝ

Detail of Agustín transcription from Prestianni 1987, p.302